

**SOCIETY OF RESEARCH
SOFTWARE ENGINEERING**

RSE CAREER PATHWAYS - EVENT SUMMARY AND SOCIETY NEXT STEPS

CONTEXT

On the 17th June 2021 the Research Software Engineering (RSE) Society held an RSE Careers Pathway event which attracted over 200 registrations. Research Software Engineers (RSEs) come from a diverse set of backgrounds and career stages. The Society of Research Software Engineering (RSE) provides an inclusive community for all who identify with the objective of “furthering RSE practice for the benefit of society”. There have been some great successes because of the RSE community, e.g. RSE fellowship, the emergence of RSE groups and international recognition of the role of RSEs. Despite the success, our community has reflected that opportunities for RSE professionals do not offer the same levels of reward and recognition as for research only focused roles. The RSE Careers Pathway event aims to explore and expose some of the boundaries to career progression which impact on the diverse yet talented community of RSEs within the UK.

The event included presentations on the Research Concordat (Sarah King & Ellen Meek) and the Technicians Commitment (Simon Breeden) as well as presentations from RSEs in the community at a range of careers stages, including junior RSEs. UKRI is a signatory and key stakeholder in the Researcher Development Concordat (the concordat) and the Technician Commitment (the TC) which set out a series of principles and obligations to be followed by research institutions in supporting talent development. It was anticipated prior to the event that some parts of our community may align to these initiatives while others may not. The event provided an opportunity to explore where these initiatives may help or hinder RSE career progression, discuss the limitations of fixed university job families, identify gaps which existing initiatives do not address, and offer an opportunity to explore broader factors which affect recognition and reward.

The outcomes of the event aimed to;

- Shape the Society strategy around engagement with UKRI and other stakeholders
- Ensure that UKRI understand the communities barriers to career progression
- Highlight career progression challenges to RSE leaders so that they can provide better opportunities
- Provide a safe space to share and exchange ideas with colleagues

This document provides an executive summary of the event, describes the key themes from each activity within the event as well as notes and responses to questions raised to the panel.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

An executive summary of the events main findings is as follows;

- RSE is a role and not a title. The role of RSE is undertaken by a diverse community which is represented by a broad mixture of academic, research and technical/professional service staff.
- UKRI and the TC emphasised the commitment towards career support of RSEs regardless of any initiative that an individual feels most closely aligned with.
- UKRI is committed through both the concordat and TC action plans to engage with research organisations and the wider community to understand financial and non-financial barriers to career progression and ensure that UKRI funding is flexible enough to support research organisations to develop bespoke career paths.
- Research organisations have a very fixed view of research vs. non research roles which is reported to be detrimental to recognising and rewarding contributions made by RSEs who see their position as a hybrid between research and technical.
- Clarification is needed from UKRI to avoid any unintentional harm caused by administrative processes giving an external perception that RSEs are exclusively technicians.

COMMUNITY PRESENTATIONS

Community presentations were provided by;

1. **Louise Brown** (University of Nottingham) – Louise talked about the role and challenges of being an “Academic RSE”. In particular, her talk discussed the challenge of being employed as an academic while identifying as a research software engineer. It was noted that there is a trade off between having the academic freedom to provide leadership (and drive forwards the RSE community) versus the lack of wider recognition for RSE outputs compared to the normal expectations of an academic.
2. **Luke Abraham** (NCAS Cambridge) – Luke talked about his experience of working within the National Centre for Atmospheric Science, a NERC research centre distributed across several institutions. It was reported that by following the university career track it was possible to achieve promotion to Senior Research Associate (Lecturer level) and Principal Research Associate (Reader equivalent). One of the challenges of a distributed centre however was reported as a disparity between the career progression frameworks (and the expectations of these relating to RSEs) of the different institutions involved.
3. **Matthew Machin** (University of Manchester) – Matt talked about his professional services role, leading a team of 13 digital health researchers, RSEs, designers and project managers. Matt raised a widely shared concern about where his role fits with respect to career progression. It was reported that his hybrid role made typical academic progression difficult but that his duties with respect to research hindered typical managerial professional service progression.
4. **Jeremy Cohen** (Imperial College London) – Jeremy brought the perspective of an ongoing/current EPSRC RSE Fellow and talked about the important role in which universities can fill in supporting RSEs through both Research and Professional service contracts. It was noted that in the absence of a “RSE career pathway” guidance is required on how institutions can support the diverse range of RSEs that exist between these two career pathways.

DISCUSSION GROUPS

Attendees of the event were invited to participate in breakout discussions which were chaired by society trustees and members of the community who ensured that discussions were conducted according to the Society of RSE code of conduct. Conversations were held under “Chatham House” rule and as such the following summary does not attribute any aspects of the conversation to individuals or organisations.

On the topic of the role and recognition of RSEs a broad range of topics were discussed. A number of breakout discussions reported that the role of RSEs were not well recognised by research organisations. In particular, software outputs were reported to not have the same perceived equity as more traditional research outputs and aspects such as the research assessment framework can exacerbate this. The implications of this go beyond financial reward and it was reported that lack of recognition affects job satisfaction and mental health. With respect to specific contributions on software there was a reported problem between novel software development and software maintenance. The former is more likely to signify a specific release and qualify as a research output whereas the latter is more difficult in quantifying personal contribution. The breakout groups clearly identified that there is a very diverse set of people who identify with the RSE role. This diversity includes organisational placement (i.e. central group vs embedded); and contract type (i.e. research vs professional services). There is however a shared frustration regarding a number of areas. E.g. The prevalence of fixed term contracts, the use of open ended contracts being tied to research funding as opposed to being permanent positions, a lack of opportunity for leadership activities (i.e. leading or co-leading research projects), a lack of recognition on papers where a significant software contribution has been made, and a feeling of not fitting within an organisations fixed job families (including for senior RSE roles). There is a reported disparity of esteem between research and technical roles that extends to those RSEs who are employed on research contracts but whose primary role is to develop research software rather than publish novel research results.

DISCUSSION GROUPS CONT.

On the topic of career progression the breakout rooms discussed a wide range of topics focusing on specific perceived challenges faced by RSEs. It was highlighted that RSE is a role and not a specific job title as such it is to be expected that RSE career progression is diverse. There is often a perception that the job title of RSE reflects those in centralised groups and care must be taken in considering career progression to the RSE community that this is inclusive of all including RSEs embedded within specific disciplines or groups. There was a reported shared concern of the career path structure used by many research organisations which is typically fixed silos for research and other (e.g. technical and professional services). This is not reflective of roles such as RSEs which span these boundaries and as such the process for progression can be challenging. There was also some concern that the UKRIs reliance on the concordat and TC emphasised the boundary between “research” and “not-research” rather than supporting those communities which span between. Many of the RSE community are part of the numerous RSE groups which have grown in popularity since the formation of the RSE association. Attendees reported that this hierarchy presented both positive and negative consequences. While groups were more likely to have clear routes for progression to more senior roles it was reported that the hierarchy does impose constraints if limited to a single top level “head of RSE” leadership position. Outside of groups (RSEs embedded within research groups) there was frustration that there was significantly less career structure in place. Many of the issues reported around clarity of career progression are also shared between roles outside of RSE. Participants highlighted similar issues regarding progression clarity for the data engineering and bioinformaticians communities. RSEs on “professional service and technical career pathway” reported some specific challenges. It was highlighted that professional services roles are frequently unable to apply for promotion. Rather than promotion, a process of “regrading” is used which is based on the business need for a specific role, rather than rewarding personal contribution. This is significantly different to a research pathway and as such there were reported cases of RSEs feeling compelled to move pathways to have an opportunity to achieve promotion. Equally, RSEs on “research” track roles have unique challenges. Although it was reported that academic career pathways are becoming more flexible in recognising a broader range of research outputs, the broader contributions that RSEs make are sometimes more difficult to align with promotion criteria. There were several cases where RSEs on research pathways highlighted that the link between senior RSE and senior research fellow was particularly unclear.

On the topic of what the Society of RSE should do to support RSE careers a number of suggestions were made within the discussions. Specifically it was suggested that the society could; engage more with individual research organisations, share more examples of job descriptions, provide professional career support (non-technical) and highlight a broader range of success stories to help motivate competing research organisations.

Q&A AND OFFLINE RESPONSES

The Q&A Panel was chaired/moderated by Paul Richmond (Society of RSE) and made up of;

- Sarah King - EPSRC
- Simon Breeden – The Technicians Commitment
- Ellen Meek - UKRI
- Mark Turner – University of Newcastle
- James Hetherington – University College London
- Alys Brett – Cullum Centre for Fusion

The panel responsively answered questions from the community which were voted on by participants using sli.do. Following the completion of the event the panel were asked to respond offline (via a Google document) to questions which received more than a single vote.

Unsurprisingly one of the key areas for questioning was around the most appropriate career pathway for RSEs. In addition to this, participants were keen to understand which initiatives, i.e. the concordat and the TC, UKRI planned on using to support the RSE community. The questions raised indicated a view (supported by the breakout discussions) that RSEs are neither exclusively researchers or technicians. There was a strong response from the panel that regardless of any initiative used to support career progression we should work together to support, and celebrate the diversity of roles within research as well as the existing initiatives used to expand on recognition and reward. UKRI clarified that “all people working in research and innovation will benefit irrespective of which initiatives they most strongly identify with”. UKRI have however indicated that administratively many of their actions relevant to RSEs will fall under the remit of the Technician Commitment when it comes to internal reporting. This should not be confused with the external perception of how RSEs can be included in research projects. EPSRC highlighted how RSEs can be (and infrequently are) costed into research proposals as co-applicants and UKRI clarified their intention to expand this beyond EPSRCs remit by using the TC. An important point was made that both the internal administrative reporting and plans for wider support for RSEs in other funding agencies must be extremely careful to not externally identify all RSEs as technicians. The implications of doing so would cause unintentional harm for the RSE community including damaging the successful operating models of many of the ~30 central RSE groups operating in the UK.

Q&A AND OFFLINE RESPONSES CONT.

An important area of questioning for career progression was around the flexibility of RSE roles to demonstrate leadership and participate in professional development. There was a view that such activities can be more difficult to schedule for RSEs embedded on projects or RSEs without the freedom of an academic role. UKRI and the TC clarified some expectations regarding this.

Importantly, UKRI sets specific action plans to support the professional development of staff funded via UKRI grants. Research organisations are expected to adhere to these regardless of their institutional support of either the concordat or the TC. The TC Action Plan in particular sets very specific demands on organisations in terms of developing and nurturing talent. The general approach by UKRI is one of incentivising research organisations to develop staff rather than punishing them.

For RSEs in purely technical roles there were a range of questions which aimed to understand the potential for career progression. It was highlighted that many institutions have quite low upper limits (in terms of grade points) on purely technical roles. These are often unable to compensate RSEs adequately for the contribution to research that they make. The TC is very clearly aiming to improve the career pathways and recognition of purely technical roles. Once again, the diversity of the community suggests that a 'one size fits all' approach should not be mandated by UKRI in terms of prescribing how organisations should support their staff. This is particularly true of RSEs who sit somewhere between the extremes of purely "research" or "technical" roles. It was acknowledged that more generally, industry tends to be better at creating purely technical career pathways and the TC should learn from this. Retaining technically gifted staff can be a challenge however it was highlighted that RSEs leaving to enter industry should not necessarily be seen as a failure to retain talent but a necessary part of delivering a highly skilled workforce. An important consideration is that the movements of RSEs between research and industry should not be one way. I.e. It is important that industry RSEs are motivated to move into research organisations and that pathways exist to support this.

Diversity of backgrounds featured heavily in the questioning and UKRI have outlined their ambitions to ensure that they deliver the UK Governments Research Roadmap. It was acknowledged that diversity in teams is critical and different backgrounds and experience can bring different ideas. There was a broad consensus that research organisations need to look at broader routes into roles supporting, facilitating and innovating around research delivery. This includes the potential for apprenticeships and encouraging migration of expertise from industry into the research sector. UKRI highlighted that they will encourage diversity by ensuring that research organisations are able to nurture and support talent from all backgrounds and experiences. This includes having a diverse set of entry points to ensure that industry technology professionals can become talented research software engineers within a research organisation. There were specific questions raised about industrial entry points where the lack of a PhD may be perceived as detrimental to career progression. A cultural change is required to have "parity of esteem" between different entry routes as, historically, recognition is achieved through obtaining a PhD.

EVENT FEEDBACK RESULTS

The event feedback which attracted 33 responses asked the community which aspects of the event they enjoyed the most. This was quite evenly distributed between the Panel Discussion, Breakout Discussions and Community Presentations sharing equal votes of ~24%. A similar distribution was observed for the least informative aspect of the event suggesting that the range of activities were broadly appropriate. In a survey of which initiative (concordat or TC) individuals felt related to them there was a broad range of opinion which reflects previous findings where similar questions have been asked (e.g. the RSE Careers session at the collaborations workshop 2021). Roughly 50% of people identify with the concordat, 38% with the TC and 44% feel a RSE specific initiative is required. Only ~9% of people identified with neither answer. A small number of people ~6% felt a research technology professionals initiative would be most appropriate and a similar number (~6%) felt that both applied to them.

SUMMARY AND NEXT STEPS

The range of activities within the RSE careers pathway event stimulated some excellent discussion which succeeded in exploring and exposing some of the boundaries to career progression impacting RSEs within the UK. As a result of this event and the summary included within the document, several suggestions/recommendations for next steps are made. It should be noted that these typically relate to the RSEs within research organisations who represented the majority of attendees at the event. Industrial RSEs likely face alternative career progression challenges which were not explored.

1. The Society should feedback the outcomes of this event into its next iteration of the RSE strategy.
2. The society should continue to share job adverts relating to RSE positions to ensure that these are accessible to the community
3. The society should proceed with its ongoing plans to deliver professional development support for RSEs.
4. Clarification should be sought from UKRI regarding the internal administrative process in which RSE career support will be provided through the Technicians Commitment. This will ensure that there is no unintentional harm caused such as the exclusion of RSEs whose roles align most closely with research, or by creating a perception that RSEs should only be funded on projects using mechanisms for technical positions (which would exclude overheads). Doing so will ensure that UKRI are able to support all RSEs regardless of which initiative they most closely align with.
5. Clarification should be sought on the process for including RSEs as co-investigators on research grants. This is currently permitted and encouraged within EPSRC and other funding councils should follow this excellent example.
6. UKRI should continue to raise awareness of the diversity of roles which contribute to research. The siloed approach to career pathways should be discouraged and research organisations should be encouraged to embrace the diversity of roles that contribute to the research lifecycle.
7. Finally, the RSE community is a leading example of non-traditional roles within research organisations, vital to the delivery of world leading science. It should be considered and consulted when setting expectations of research organisations, policy and guidance for research funding and in the delivery of mechanisms to improve talent development.

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APPENDIX A

Notes from Q&A Session on Research Software Engineering Career Pathways

Concerning the EPSRC fellowship, how many funded applicants were part of an RSE group within a university compared to a domain specific research group?

- Not sure
- Sarah to comment offline
- **Comment from Sarah** - From the information I have on the RSE Fellowships that have been awarded to date approximately $\frac{1}{4}$ are employed in RSE groups within an institution and $\frac{3}{4}$ are employed within a domain specific research group.

RSEs aren't researchers or technicians so they lack a policy that universities can sign up to. Should the Society be writing a RSE Concordat/Commitment that will help UKRI support them?

- Work together, rather than against each other
- Don't say "we're not them" -> hurt them
- Broader recognition is common goal
- Word "technician" has different meanings, includes RSEs in the commitment

Do we have the non-survivorship-bias case studies from the people who "dropped out" of RSE career trajectories and understanding of what went wrong?

- Two types of examples: one remains in the uni, different type of position (outside research), other came from contractor, then got higher (industry) offer
- Other examples: nothing went wrong, but other opportunities -> It's not a failure

What is the RSE career pathway? Are there good examples of this in the University sector (beyond one or two examples)? Universities don't yet know how to deal with this progression. The pathway does not exist in many places (does it in any?)?

- For technicians, has a broad definition which brought its own difficulties, had to hop between different roles to develop roles, very ad-hoc, now there is a better understanding of skills needed. Value (esteem) of technical specialism vs managerial has to be increased.
- Technical manager probably similar? Technicians have more structured job family.

Should permanent RSE roles contain a similar level of self-directed time as many research grants offer Postdocs? There's a lot of maintenance work on long-running projects that doesn't fit into existing funding structures well.

- Not seen in standard grant
- Time for career development is important
- For RAs, it depends very much on the PI
- It could happen that if you start costing it in, if you don't it's no longer expected/allowed
- Should not depend on the type of grant -> grant guidance

APPENDIX A

Notes from Q&A Session on Research Software Engineering Career Pathways - Cont.

How do private employers who hire software engineers in research (for example, Microsoft Research has RSEs) manage their career structures, and what can we learn from them?

- How do pure-technical people “climb up”? -> Big-picture technical solutions instead of managerial work
- Several technical senior levels based on expertise
- Often niche (defined by a single researcher)
- Technical promotion track without people management, equivalent to academic track

RSEs outside EPSRC often appear as named researchers rather than co-applicants, this being the only way of recognising their significant contribution to the workplan. Do either the concordat/TC offer a route for improving this situation ?

- Technicians work on it, much improved (recognize technical and academic input into grants) -> not there yet, but made progress
- **Addition from UKRI:** During our presentation we flagged that UKRI’s TC action plan has a specific action around this to ‘amend the eligibility for our grants so that technicians contributing to the intellectual leadership and management of a project can apply for funding where they can be supported by their organisation to do so’. RSEs are considered under our work on the concordat and TC therefore this action also applies to RSEs. As mentioned, EPSRC already allow RSEs as co-applicants and the TC gives a route for this to be looked at more broadly across research councils through working with councils to see where this would benefit their communities.
- At EPSRC RSEs as co-applicants still uncommon, but sometimes in Excalibur
- New EPSRC software call (not only large-scale novel funding, but smaller pieces of work, develop SW to next phase, software maintenance)
- Importance of SW maintenance needs to be recognised
- Knowledge Integration
- RSE have been Co-Is since 2013 at least, unis often do not know about it -> make contact with research councils to clarify; creates overheads -> do not risk to lose that!

Its been great to see RSE fellowships from EPSRC, but it feels like the other research councils are lagging behind on this. Is there any sign of this changing? Has there been resistance to the idea or is just a lack of funds?

- Other research councils are very interested, no resistance
- There is career dev support for non-standard academic career path is in the pipeline
- Point to EPSRC as best practice
- Central UKRI activity

APPENDIX B

Full offline responses from the panel w.r.t. Community Questions

How do we enable researchers at smaller institutions that lack the institutional knowledge or funding to be able to access RSE support that folks at the Russell Group enjoy?

Response from UKRI: UKRI's Technician Commitment Action Plan states that as a funder, we expect the research organisations (ROs) in which we invest to recognise and value their technically skilled people and nurture them in reaching their full potential. This includes supporting their professional development as members of the research and innovation community, providing working conditions that enable them to flourish, and equipping them to use their skills across the research and innovation system, whether in the private, public or third sectors.

RSEs are included in this expectation so if a research organisation is in receipt of our funding (either grants or core funding like QR) we would expect that RSEs should be supported. We are keen to engage with the whole RSE community in the UK across all institutions to understand barriers to career development and to identify and share good practice from institutions that are already taking successful approaches to supporting their RSEs. We'd encourage the RSE community to take an inclusive approach and work together across the whole diversity of research settings and roles that RSEs inhabit to identify shared challenges and examples of good practice and to engage with UKRI and other funders on the culture change needed to improve support for RSEs and people working in research and innovation more broadly.

Response from TC: It is important for the community to be clear and consistent with its messaging as a broad inclusive community, beyond the Russell Group and engage with UKRI and other funders through existing mechanisms to bring about the culture change required across the sector.

How many RSEs are failed academics?

Response from UKRI: UKRI strongly refutes the premise of this question. We know that the concept of leaving academia as 'failure' contributes to a whole range of research culture issues that harm both research and innovation and the people that work in it. UKRI is committed to supporting all people who work in research and innovation to progress their careers across the research and innovation system with porosity and mobility between the public, private and third sector at all levels and parity of esteem between different routes and roles.

APPENDIX B

Full offline responses from the panel w.r.t. Community Questions - Cont.

If we have a RSE pool scenario, like many universities now have, and are booking costs onto grants through that for partial RSE's, is there anything specific we should include in the grant application, or is RSE enough?

Response from UKRI: It's worth seeking advice from the individual funder in the first instance as this is likely to differ across research councils/funders outside of UKRI. EPSRC would expect proposals that include RSE's in the team to document this in the proposal. They should be mentioned in the staffing on the proposal and also their contribution detailed in the Case for Support and workplans. You can either just give the job title RSE as you would for a PDRA for example or name the individual. We are looking to ensure that the contribution that RSEs undoubtedly make to research outcomes is recognised and acknowledged.

For career progression to Senior RSE and then HoRSE, it seems it is culturally necessary to have a PhD. How then do I progress without one? Will my employer fund my schooling?

Response from UKRI: The UK Government's Research and Development Roadmap highlights the importance of nurturing and supporting talent from all backgrounds and experiences. The Government is due to publish its R&D People and Culture Strategy in the coming months which will build on this and look at how the UK can attract and retain a diverse research community. In order to do this we need to enable people to enter and progress their careers in research and innovation across a whole range of routes to entry and have parity of esteem between these different routes e.g. between apprenticeships/ experiential learning and more 'traditional' academic routes. UKRI is committed to working with stakeholders across the sector to support this work and drive culture change to ensure that people working in research and innovation can develop and progress their careers across a diversity of routes and career pathways.

Response from TC: This comes back to the recognition element of the day's presentations: there needs to be multiple ways for RSEs to demonstrate their skills and experience. Historically, and culturally, the predominant way to demonstrate knowledge and skills is through a PhD but that needs to be broadened out and professional registration is one mechanism for doing this. The Technician Commitment is a strong supporter of this so colleagues can demonstrate to potential employers the breadth of experience of skills and experience they have knowing it has been externally validated.

APPENDIX B

Full offline responses from the panel w.r.t. Community Questions - Cont.

Should RSE groups be recruiting people with essential computing skills but who lack any formal academic research experience?

Response from UKRI: The UK Government's Research and Development Roadmap highlights the importance of nurturing and supporting talent from all backgrounds and experiences. The Government is due to publish its R&D People and Culture Strategy in the coming months which will build on this and look at how the UK can attract and retain a diverse research community. In order to do this we need to enable people to enter and progress their careers in research and innovation across a whole range of routes to entry and have parity of esteem between these different routes e.g. between apprenticeships/ experiential learning and more 'traditional' academic routes. UKRI is committed to working with stakeholders across the sector to support this work and drive culture change to ensure that people working in research and innovation can develop and progress their careers across a diversity of routes and career pathways.

Response from TC: It is important for Universities and Research Institutes to look beyond their own sector to identify people from whichever sphere they come from to develop new ways of working: diversity in teams is critical and different backgrounds and experience can bring different ideas.

At our university, the 'Technician' job family stops at Senior level, being considered a technician would be harmful to our career prospects. To what degree are funders able to force universities to change their job families for fairness?

Response from UKRI: Through initiatives such as the Researcher Development Concordat and the TC, UKRI are looking at ways that we can incentivise research organisations to invest in supporting the careers of all people working in research and innovation. This includes through research assessment and grant terms and conditions. Research organisations may take a range of approaches to supporting career development and progression of the staff that they employ based on the needs of their communities therefore there is unlikely to be a 'one size fits all' approach that could or should be mandated by UKRI. Instead UKRI has committed through our concordat and TC action plans to engage with research organisations and the wider community to understand financial and non-financial barriers to career progression and ensure that our funding is flexible enough to support research organisations to develop bespoke career paths. In the longer term we aim to explore the impacts that different funding models have on the career development and sustainability of different roles such as RSEs and develop pilot schemes for sustainable funding of career paths and technical posts.

Response from TC: Many universities through engagement with the Technician Commitment are in the process of developing career pathways for technicians that embed parity of esteem with all colleagues through sharing of good practice across the sector.

APPENDIX B

Full offline responses from the panel w.r.t. Community Questions - Cont.

Just to be clear: UKRI are going to treat RSEs as both researchers and technicians because they're both? (It sometimes sounds like they're just being classified only as technicians by UKRI?)

JH notes: It's important that costing decisions are not impacted by universities' internal organisational structures. When a role moves from being in an individual research group on a precarious postdoc contract, to part of a pool of staff scientists, the nature of the work does not change. Therefore, the overheads/fEC model should treat RSEs in staff scientist pools the same as RSEs hired as per-project DI postdocs. Similarly, this should also not be impacted whether the university labels such a pool as part of a research department, a library, or in IT. ("Professional services".)

JH notes: UKRI's intent is to see the "101 roles that change the world" treated well and expanded. This is laudable. Treating what are currently high-skilled groups of staff scientist professionals the same as 'technicians' has a noble lack of snobbery. However, one must be careful to avoid unintentional harm: if this forces RSEs back into short-term postdoc roles in order for universities to continue to be able to attract overheads on this work, that would be a retrograde step.

Response from UKRI: UKRI have aligned our approach and our action plans for the concordat and TC to ensure that all people working in research and innovation will benefit irrespective of which initiatives they most strongly identify with and in acknowledgement of the fact that there are often porous boundaries between different role families in research and innovation. As the TC has more of a focus on career pathways that fall outside of a 'traditional' academic career pathway many of the actions most relevant to RSEs will fall administratively under the remit of the TC in terms of how UKRI will report internally against these initiatives. UKRI's definition of technician, along with the definition used by the Technician Commitment itself, is sufficiently broad and inclusive to include RSEs. We acknowledge that RSEs may more strongly identify with one/both/neither of the concordat/TC but this does not affect our approach, which is focused on engaging with the RSE community to understand their needs and the barriers they face and using the existing tools of the concordat and TC to drive positive change for RSEs and all people working in research and innovation.

Limited mention of research data engineering and research infrastructure engineering at this event - how different do/should their career pathways look?

Response from TC: Any career development framework should aim to be inclusive of all within the community so career pathways for research data/infrastructure engineering should be contained within that.

APPENDIX B

Full offline responses from the panel w.r.t. Community Questions - Cont.

Is there any incentive for employers to join the concordat/technician commitment?

Response from UKRI: In its concordat and TC action plans UKRI outlines its expectation that the research organisations (ROs) in which we invest recognise and value their people and nurture them in reaching their full potential. Research organisations may choose to do this through the auspices of the concordat and TC, which we know are highly effective tools for driving culture change, or they may choose other routes. We expect them to meet our expectations irrespective of whether they are signatories to the concordat/TC. In our action plans we have committed to incentivising research organisations to support the careers and development of their people through grant terms and conditions and research assessment.

Response from TC: Yes. For Universities and Research Institutes to thrive, and even survive, they need to value and support their entire workforce. Both of these initiatives allow the sector and its constituent institutions to clearly demonstrate that support and promote engagement with, and empowerment of all staff to deliver a new research and innovation culture.

Recognition is important in any role. What does recognition look like for an RSE and how can we get it?

Response from TC: Recognition of the skills and experience of a RSE is for the community to help develop, within the values and drivers of the Technician Commitment in terms of recognition align very well with professional registration either through the Science Council or a number of professional bodies covering the broad spectrum of technician roles.